

POLITENESS IN WOMEN'S DISCOURSE IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Abstract: Politeness is a phenomenon which is common to all cultures. Each culture has a different perception of what is polite and each language has various devices for expressing politeness. One of the important aspects of politeness which is the central focus of many studies is the polite behaviors of men and women. The focus of this study is on the politeness strategies of males and females from different aspects. The main point of this article is to portray gender language politeness which analyzes the description of the connection of gender and language politeness within the frame of speech acts based on gender. The strategy utilized in this inquire about is clear subjective. The technique used in collecting data through direct observation and recording. Determination of the compliance and deviation of the principle of politeness of language is based on indicators of politeness of language derived from Leech's theory. The technique of data analysis in this study is the transcription of data from the records; identify, classify and draw conclusions.

Keywords: Politeness, Gender, Politeness Behaviors of Males and Females

Introduction

Politeness is a social behavior common to all cultures. It is a major element of every day interaction. The politeness concept can be studied linguistically (verbally) or nonlinguistically (non-verbally). The focus of this study is linguistic politeness that is the way of being polite to others by the use of language. Understanding people's polite ways of talking can be a great help to the communication gap between women and men and a giant step towards opening lines of communication.

According to Leech (1983), politeness is interpreted as a treatment that can reduce shifts in an interaction. The use of language must be subtle, polite civilized, gentle treatment, and virtuous in an effort to reduce conflict or shift. According to Ferguson (1986), politeness applies when a contract of conversation is used by speakers and listeners as an effort to perpetuate harmony communication without causing conflict. Politeness does not refer to politeness solely in language but also refers to nonverbal aspects such as behavior, facial expressions, and tone of voice. Fraser and Nolan (1981) argued

that politeness is valid if a contract of conversation used by the speaker and listener intended to perpetuate a harmonious relationship in communication. Brown and Levinson (1987) consider politeness as an attempt to reduce the Face Threat Actions

(TAM) in conversations with listeners. In the context of language politeness, Omar (2000) links it with the use of everyday language that does not cause anger, anger and offense from the listener. This will create an atmosphere of harmonious relations between the speaker and the listener.

According to Grundy (2000), politeness is “the term we use to describe the extent to which actions, including the way things are said, match addressees’ perceptions of how they should be performed,” (cited in bloomer, Griffiths & Merrison, 2005, p. 111). Yule (2006, p. 119) also defined it as “showing awareness of and consideration for another person’s face.” Hill et al. (1986) along the same line, defined politeness as “one of the constraints on human interaction, whose purpose is to consider others’ feelings, establish levels of mutual comfort, and promote rapport” (cited in watts 2003, p. 51). Watts (2003) defined linguistic politeness as “an abstract term referring to a wide variety of social strategies for constructing and reproducing cooperative social interaction across cultures” (p. 47). Linguistic politeness has been the area of extensive research since the works of Lakoff in the 1970s and those of brown and Levinson in the 1980s. According to Lakoff (2004), politeness linguistically is concerned with verbal communication and nonlinguistically is concerned with other aspects of communication such as body language. Brown and Levinson (1987) have been amongst the pioneers of linguistic politeness research for 20 years. Their studies into politeness were concerned with the concept of face taken from Goffman (1967), the image that a speaker or hearer would like to maintain during the course of an interaction.

The fact that female speech tends to be polite has been discussed in previous sections. Since maxims are principles that form politeness, their expression in female speech goes without saying. Women use the maxim of generosity in their speech mainly in directives, since a directive is a form of an illocutionary (speech) act, and the activity of women in most cases depends on their communication skills.

Within a certain sociolinguistic environment, the expression of the maxim of generosity in female speech can have a different character. For example, in a social group where intergender subordination is built on the basis of strict stereotypes (for example, Uzbek social groups), women widely use the maxim of

generosity in their speech, since the maxim of generosity is characterized by attitude. So, when a woman belonging to an Uzbek social group gives instructions to others, following her natural principles of politeness and obedience (mainly to men), she automatically builds her speech based on the maxim of generosity. In addition, a woman belonging to an Uzbek social group (in other words, an Uzbek author) usually does not force the addressee to do anything, giving a directive is one of the main signals of the maxim of generosity. For example:

“– Додаси, жиянингизга қўнғироқ қила олмайсизми? Йўқ бўлса, ўзим қўнғироқ қила қоламан” (an excerpt from a typical dialogue). – (“Dodasi, can't you call your niece? If not, I'll call myself.”)

Or by looking at the two replicas given:

“–Менга ёрдам бермасангиз, қийналиб кетаман”

“–Мен бу ишни Сизнинг ёрдамингиз билан анча тезроқ битира олардим”.

The meaning of both passages is almost the same - the conditional woman asks the interlocutor to help her in her work. The remark in the first sentence imposes a condition on the interlocutor: building an address in this direction is completely contrary to the maxim of generosity; and the appearance of this appeal in the second replica is an example of a vivid expression of the maxim of generosity - a woman expresses her directive to her interlocutor in an indirect form, without inviting the interlocutor to any "problem" and without forcing him to Do anything.

J. Thomas notes that the expression of the maxim of generosity in the speech of women belonging to the English language and social groups is characterized by showing the interlocutor that his (the interlocutor's) interests are the most important for the speaker (in the case of a woman). At the same time, the maxim of generosity can be expressed both in verbal and non-verbal actions. For example:

“–Take a rest, you are tired. I'll clean the room” (“Дамингизни олиб туринг, сиз чарчадингиз. Мен хонани ўзим йиғиштираман”).

The above primitive example shows the expression of the maxim of generosity in the speech of a woman belonging to the English sociolinguistic group - the speaker saw that the listener was tired and could not physically move, so he took over the work.

In the speech of women, the maxim of generosity is often expressed next to the maxim of modesty, which can be explained as follows: both maxims are based on the speech character of a woman (modesty, benevolence). However, the

meaning of the maxim in a woman's speech has a different degree of relevance: despite the fact that the maxim of generosity affects what a woman says, the maxim of generosity prevails over the maxim of generosity. It is worth noting that the subjects of communication can express several maxims in their speech at the same time (implicit expression).

Conclusion

In this part, the findings of females' politeness strategies, males' politeness strategies and the relationship between participants which affect the use of their politeness strategies are discussed. Moreover, the results are compared with the previous studies to see whether they are corresponding or not.

However a study of Brown (1980) on Mayan community showed that sometimes women were less polite than men. He claimed that these behaviors were due to social differences in the position of women and men in the society. It is interesting that Brown (1980) challenged this view that women speak more politely than men. He believes that socio-cultural factors of each community should be taken into consideration. He stated "the link between behavior and a social structure also provide a basis for prediction about when and where and under what conditions women's speech will take on certain characteristics" (Brown, 1980, p. 22). Therefore, it is better to link women or men politeness behaviors to a social structure and culture in a specific community. The findings of this study indicate that the politeness behaviors of males and females depend on many factors such as gender of the listeners and the relationship between listeners and the speakers. Moreover, the role of culture should not be dismissed.

On the whole, it can be concluded that it is true that women try to be more polite in order to maintain an aesthetically acceptable appearance to avoid the risk of rejection and stigma, but politeness behaviors of women and men are culture sensitive and many factors should be taken into consideration in order to examine their politeness strategies. For example, in this study it was seen that if a male stranger pushes a woman passing by, the woman become angry and try to express her anger by use of body language or uttering a word, but if a woman pushes them suddenly, most of women show no reaction.

This kind of behavior has a root in our culture and society and it can be different from other societies. Brown (1980) stated "by linking behavior to social structure we are enabled to ask the question why do women talk the way they do in the society and what social structure, pressure and constraints are modeling behavior".

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